

Description of the ultrasound test performed on 08/11/2022

Patient: Anna T.

HOLOGIC/Supersonic Aixplorer MACH20 apparatus, L18-5 probe

Left breast and right armpit:

Intangible Changes: at 3.00, approx. 1 cm below the skin, 2 cm from the areola, there are two longitudinal lesions of similar morphology, quite regular in shape, well-circumscribed, with homogeneous echogenicity, not susceptible to pressure with a probe, with increased echo behind the lesion, size:

1. width 5.5mm, length 5mm, height 3.5mm;
2. width 5mm, length 8mm, height 3mm;

Suggested cysts.

No dilated milk ducts.

No pathological axillary lymph nodes.

Right breast and right armpit:

Palpable lesion (focal palpable lesion): at 11.00, approx. 1 cm below the skin, 3 cm from the areola, there is a longitudinal lesion, irregular in shape, quite well-defined, size: width 8 mm, length 10 mm, height 6 mm, with slightly heterogeneous echogenicity, not susceptible to compression probe. In shear-wave elastography, the average is 83.5 kPa.

Suggested fibroadenoma, but other lesion is also possible.*Ref.

No dilated milk ducts.

No pathological axillary lymph nodes.

Conclusion and recommendation:

BIRADS 4a for mammotome biopsy

In earlier studies, a change that was more in favor of FAD.

*Ref. Park, S.Y., Choi, J.S., Han, BK. et al. Shear wave elastography in the diagnosis of breast non-mass lesions: factors associated with false negative and false positive results. *Eur Radiol* **27**, 3788–3798 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-017-4763-6>